

Tracer Study of Senior High School Graduates in Kalangyawon National High School

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11180054](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11180054)

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Abstract

This research study sought to know the career choices of the Senior High School graduates at Kalangyawon National High School during the School Year 2023-2024 as the basis for the recommendation plan. The demographic profile of the participants was determined in terms of age, gender, civil status, track and strand, year graduated, and highest educational attainment, and the career choice of senior high school graduates in terms of college degrees, courses taken, occupations, reasons for unemployment, employment status, types of occupations, places of work, types of businesses, and middle skills development, which were analyzed using frequency and percentage. Additionally, the senior high school career pathways of the participants were examined and interpreted through thematic analysis. A mixed-method approach of descriptive quantitative and qualitative analysis was employed, using a survey questionnaire. Seventy-nine (79) participants were selected through stratified random sampling. The findings revealed that most participants are pursuing higher education and have chosen the Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (BSA) as their degree program. Furthermore, seventy-seven (77) percent of the participants who completed senior high school opted for TVL-Agri Crop Production. Moreover, twenty-eight (28) percent of the participants were employed, with a majority having temporary employment status. Forty-six (46) percent of the participants were involved in agriculture businesses and sixty-one (61) percent of the participants obtained an Agriculture Crop Production NCII Tesda Certificate. Based on the results, findings, and conclusions, it is advisable to implement the recommendation plan to enhance the Senior High School program while continuing the TVET Agri-Fishery program.

Keywords: Senior High School Graduates, Curriculum Exits, Tracer Study, Kalangyawon National High School, Carcar City

Introduction

Tracer study is a research method commonly used in education and workforce development to track the progress and outcomes of graduates. It involves tracing the paths of individuals who have completed a particular program, and overall contributions to society for ongoing development and relevance in the ever-changing field of education. Career choice in Senior High School is the decision-making process undertaken by students upon completing their Senior High School education regarding their future career paths. This involves selecting from a range of options such as college degree, courses taken, reasons for unemployment, employment status, types of occupation, place of work, type of business, and middle skills development. One of the primary aims of the K-12 program is to produce senior high school graduates who are prepared for the workforce. This is achieved by establishing a functional basic education system that will ensure productive and responsible citizens who possess the values, competencies, and skills necessary for both employment and lifelong learning under Republic Act No. 10533, Section 2 (Enhance Basic Education Act 2013). In the 2019 report of the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), the unemployment rate for junior high school graduates was 28.2%. College graduates came in second at 20.9%, followed by freshmen at 8.2%. The graduate's unemployment was attributed to a number of factors, including a lack of real job training skills and reluctance on the part of domestic employers to hire recent SHS graduates. For instance, based on the studies of the Philippine Business for Education, while the first batch of senior high school graduates theoretically possess 93% of the competencies, 20% of the 70 leading companies in the country are inclined to hire SHS graduates (Yee, 2018). This tracer study of senior high school graduates is to assess the alumni about their career choices and to determine how well the curriculum exits they pursued for their life after graduation.

Literature Review

The Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), performed a survey that found that in 2015, 1.6 million people completed vocational courses and 656,498 students graduated from college. Based on the study conducted by (DOLE) they have identified 275 jobs are in demand, with 105 of them being hard-to-fill occupations. De Guzman, A. (2015) stated that the majority of students wanted to continue their education in college because, from the perspective of the Filipino people, education is vital to the nation's development and makes them better, productive members of society. Education contributes to addressing the issue of unemployment, which hinders the country's progress. UNESCO (2006) stated that in general education, TVET refers to "aspects of the educational process involving the study of technologies and related sciences, as well as the development of useful abilities and mindsets, knowledge and comprehension of people who work in different spheres of the economy and society."

Aure M.R., et al., (2019) stated that the tracer study emphasizes that education mismatches appear to capture distinct effects on workers both financially and non-financially. Staunton, T. (2015) stated that deciding on the student’s personality is the best career or education path and provides a better career. Rogan M. & Reynolds, J. (2016) stated that a graduate tracer study is helpful for education policy and equity implications. Son, H. (2007) work, "The Role of Labor Market in Explaining Growth and Inequality: The Philippines Case," provided the study’s theoretical foundation stating that higher-educated people have increasingly displaced less educated people from the workforce. De Ocampo, M.B., Bogano, A.J., and Tan, A (2012) stated that the employability of graduates is frequently examined by educational institutions using tracer studies. CIIT Philippines School Multimedia Arts, Web Design, Mobile Game Development (2018) stated that the growth of the economy and increased trade, there is a tremendous need for graduates with your qualifications. The first graduating class of senior high school in our country has just completed. Regarding the readiness of the batch of K12 finishers, opinions vary. But most graduates are competitive when it comes to showcasing their skills. These young professionals have completed their senior high school education and are equipped with the information and mindset needed to succeed in the workforce. Thankfully, more businesses are emerging as a result of the growing demand for professions in multimedia arts, web design, 3D animation, and mobile game development among recent high school graduates. Ramanick et al. (2015), training program evaluation and improvement depend heavily on the graduates accomplishment of their individual goals and plans. Graduation tracking will help colleges and universities replace the prevailing subjective evidence-“Because the graduates and their parents tell them they have succeeded”- with the “hard data” that those outside evaluators are more requesting. All colleges and universities must create a system for gathering hard data as proof in order to fend off invasive state thrusts.

Methodology

This study used a mixed method of descriptive quantitative and qualitative. Data is collected from demographic profiles, including age, gender, civil status, track, strand, year graduated, and highest educational attainment. The study uses frequency and percentage formulas to analyze demographic profiles and career choices in terms of; college degree, courses taken, occupation, unemployment reasons, employment status, types of occupation, place of work, and middle skills development. Thematic Analysis (TA) is used to interpret questions and document reviews of alumni’s career pathways. Data was collected through a survey questionnaire administered through Google Forms and stratified random sampling.

Results and Discussion

A tracer study of Senior High School graduates entails tracking the educational pathways and outcomes of graduates based on the curriculum they followed during their study. The study surveyed 79 participants, mostly female 51.90% and aged 19-23 with 73.42%. The majority are single at 87.34% and TVL Agri-Fishery tracks with 77.22%. Moreover, the career choices there were 43 or equivalent to 28.69% who pursued college, 28% of the participants were employed, 46.15% had an agriculture business, and 61% received an Agriculture Crop Production NCII TESDA Certificate.

**Table 5
Track and Strand Completed in Senior High School of the Participants**

Track and Strand	Frequency (%)	Percentage (%)
TVL (Agri-Fishery Arts)	61	77.22
Academic (HUMSS)	18	22.78
Total	79	100

Table 5 shows the completion of Senior High School tracks there was 77.22 percent completed Agri-Fishery (TVL) while 22.78 percent completed Academic (HUMSS) with a total of 100 percent. There were 21.52 percent from the batch 2022-2023 was the highest frequency of participants. This differs from the results of the studies of Padios et al. (2021) and Gido (2022) where they found that TVL is more popular among the participants.

**Table 7
College degree of the Participants**

College Degree	Frequency (%)	Percentage (%)
Currently pursuing higher education	43	55.13
Not pursuing college	35	44.87
Total	78	100

Table 7 presents the graduates currently pursuing higher education there were 55.13%, while 44.87% are not. Graduate tracer studies are crucial for higher education institutions to adapt to societal changes and employer demands by evaluating and reviewing curricula (Cañizares, 2015). Moreover, there was 28.69% college level. The study shows that most of the answers of the alumni based on the four curriculum exits are pursuing higher education.

The Philippine Qualification Framework under Executive Order No.83, s. 2012, guides curriculum development in higher education institutions to align with national standards and competencies, reflecting the focus of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) on improving education nationwide.

Table 10
Employment Status of the Participants

Employment	Frequency (%)	Percentage (%)
Employed	22	28.95
Not employed now	36	47.37
Total	76	100

The data shows that a majority of Senior High School Graduates are not employed has a frequency of 36 or equivalent to 47.37%. Reasons for not being employed include no job opportunity, family concern, health-related, lack of work experience, engaging in further study, no connections, no interest in getting a job, lack of professional eligibility, and having plans to seek a job out of the country. The highest frequency is for those engaging in further study, with most participants still pursuing their dreams in life. The top two reasons for unemployment are advanced studies. In the tracer study of Macatangay (2013), the lack of work experience is the number one reason for unemployment, followed by job opportunities and further studies.

Table 16
TESDA Certificates Received by the Participants

TESDA	Frequency (%)	Percentage (%)
Agriculture Crop Production NCII	8	61.54
Organic Agriculture Production NCII	1	7.69
Training of Trainers Certificate	1	7.69
Agriculture Crop Production NCII	1	7.69
Agri-Crop Production NCI	2	15.38
Total	13	100

Table 16, the majority of participants acquired TESDA Certificates, with 50% opting for skilled work, 43.75 for office work, and 6.25% for education or facilitator. Agri-Crop Production NCII had the highest frequency has 61.54%. This certification holds significant value, ensuring graduates possess essential skills for middle-level skilled employment (Macar,2017). Moreover, there were 19.72% perceived it as less valuable due to limited engagement in school activities.

Career Pathways of the Participants

Personal growth involves learning, developing skills, discovering oneself, and gaining confidence. Senior High School in Kalangyawon National High School emphasizes values, responsibility, and hard work to help students make informed career choices. However, many students feel their current tracks don't align with their chosen career or course, and lack experience or skills related to their chosen course. Career guidance is crucial in balancing life choices, managing work and relationships, and finding financial stability while nurturing personal connections. Balancing these aspects is like juggling different aspects of life to support oneself and those one cares about.

Conclusion

Career choice in Senior High School is the decision-making process undertaken by students upon completing their Senior High School education regarding their future career paths. This involves selecting from a range of options such as college degree, courses taken, reasons for unemployment, employment status, types of occupation, place of work, type of business, and middle skills development.

Results concluded that a majority of participants were females aged between 19-23, primarily in early career stages. The study underscores the vital role of senior high school education in guiding students toward successful careers and equipping them with necessary workforce skills. Tracer studies furnish educational institutions with data on

graduates' employability, competencies, and program effectiveness, aiding in academic enhancement. Many students' express interest in agricultural and fishery courses, revealing the influence of school subjects on career decisions, particularly in agriculture. Overall, the research highlights high school's role in preparing students for postsecondary education or the workforce, suggesting the need for curriculum updates to

better support students. Recommendations include adopting proposed study recommendations, conducting comprehensive studies, strengthening TVET Agri-Fishery tracks, and sustaining the K-12 program.

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